

ORGANIZATION OF INFORMATION AND ANALYTICAL ACTIVITIES OF INVESTIGATIVE DEPARTMENTS OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS**Turaev Dilmurod Ruzimurodovich**

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Abstract. *The article develops scientific views on the concept and essence of information analysis, the processes associated with the use of information, as well as the role of information and analytical activities in law enforcement agencies, as well as suggestions and recommendations for further improvement.*

Keywords: *information, analysis, information-analytical activity, purpose of information-analytical activity in investigative divisions, task of information-analysis, prospects of information use.*

ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННО-АНАЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СЛЕДСТВЕННЫХ ОРГАНОВ ВНУТРЕННИХ ДЕЛ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются научные взгляды на концепцию и сущность анализа информации, процессы, связанные с использованием информации, роль информационно-аналитической деятельности в правоохранительных органах, а также предложения и рекомендации по дальнейшему совершенствованию.*

Ключевые слова: *информация, анализ, информационно-аналитическая деятельность, цель информационно-аналитической деятельности в следственных подразделениях, задача информационно-аналитического анализа, перспективы использования информации.*

INTRODUCTION

Reforming the judicial system is one of the main priorities of state policy in ensuring reliable protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens and increasing access to justice. In order to adapt the activities of all sectors in our country to modern requirements and the effective use of foreign experience, information and analytical activities are important. In this regard, it should be noted that the emerging threats and challenges, in particular, international terrorism, religious extremism, illegal migration, human trafficking, the growing spread of ideas alien to our people among young people, need to prevent and eliminate them in a timely manner. puts new tasks on. Effective implementation of these tasks requires, first of all, the identification of all errors and shortcomings in the management system of law enforcement agencies and the organization of labor, the implementation of comprehensive measures to address them.

Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 16, 2017, RP-3216 "On measures to radically improve the system of training, retraining and advanced training of law enforcement officers" Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the creation of a qualitatively new system of retraining and continuous training of law enforcement officers by its educational institutions has been identified as the first priority in the development of the system of training, retraining and advanced training.

The Investigation Department under the Ministry of Internal Affairs was established to improve the activities of the Investigative Units under the Ministry of Internal Affairs, to create effective mechanisms for timely detection of crimes, comprehensive, complete and impartial

investigation, unconditional implementation of the offense, was found. the inevitability of responsibility.

The Department is responsible for a comprehensive and systematic analysis of the practice of criminal investigation, including the identification of causes and conditions of crime, as well as measures to eliminate them, the organization and coordination of investigative units of law enforcement agencies, timely detection of crimes , to ensure a comprehensive, complete and impartial investigation, unconditional observance of the rule of law in the conduct of inquiries and preliminary investigations, as well as the organization of staffing and training of investigative units, providing methodological and practical assistance to investigative units of internal affairs; as well as the direct investigation, legislation, law enforcement practice, and inquiry and investigation to develop and implement proposals for further improvement of the forms and methods of organization of the investigation.

Current and future planning of the ministry's activities by the Investigation Department, development of the main directions of development of investigative divisions of internal affairs bodies, including identification of causes and conditions of crimes, as well as taking measures to eliminate them, crime prevention and fight against crime, Further improvement of legislation, law enforcement practice and forms and methods of organization of inquiries and preliminary investigations in pre-investigation and criminal proceedings, preparation of information and analytical data on problematic issues of criminal investigation and submission of relevant proposals to the leadership of the MIA.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Information is information about individuals, objects, facts, events, happenings and processes, regardless of their sources and form of presentation.

Analysis, on the other hand, is a Greek word meaning “from the bottom up” or “completely”.

Information-analytical activity is the activity of the head of the internal affairs body aimed at ensuring the development of urgent, reasonable and effective management decisions in the implementation of law enforcement and crime control, as well as other tasks of the internal affairs body.

Thus, the need to use information and analytical activities in the system to organize the activities of investigative units of law enforcement agencies and establish an effective management system is explained by the high level.

The content of Article 12 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs" of September 16, 2016: "Internal Affairs uses scientific achievements, modern technologies and information systems" aimed at transforming it into today's popular structure by carrying out large-scale work.

As the field of information-analytical activity is one of the least studied areas, we can see that many monographs, scientific works and dissertations have been conducted by national and foreign researchers to improve it. In particular, in the researches of national researchers D.Temirov, F.Rustamov, I.Bobokulov the issues of information-analytical work, systematic analysis are widely covered. The role of information-analytical activity in decision-making, the scientific and practical significance of its introduction has been studied in the research work of foreign scientists M. Meskon, M. Albert, H. Franklin, H.Y. Folmut, D. Sadler, E. Sichakova.

However, these studies do not cover the importance and effectiveness of information and analytical activities in the investigative units of the police. The importance of information-analytical activity in investigative units has not been studied by national researchers.

According to the well-known scientist Y.V.Kurnosov, "information-analytical activity is an optimal management that allows effective processing of data and improves the quality of existing knowledge and the acquisition of new knowledge".

D.Z.Filippenkova defines the concept of information-analytical activity as "a set of information processes (data collection, retrieval, processing) necessary for a high-quality and effective management process. The collection, processing, application and transmission of information are an integral part of the success of any activity".

RESULTS

In general, information on information and analytical activities in law enforcement agencies is collected and analyzed in the following form:

- Statistics on the socio-economic, demographic and criminogenic situation in the service area;
- information on the forces and means of law enforcement agencies, the results of search operations, the state of discipline and compliance with the law;
- information and analytical data of internal affairs and other law enforcement agencies;
- information on judicial practice;
- Certificates of inspection and control over the activities of law enforcement agencies;
- Scientific research on the criminogenic situation and the fight against crime, information on the attitude of the population to the activities of law enforcement agencies;
- appeals of individuals and legal entities;
- Posters and articles in local and foreign media and Internet information on the activities of law enforcement agencies.

It should be noted that the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan on March 19, 2022 at the twenty-fourth plenary session of the Senate of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of the Department of Internal Affairs of Angren and Bostanlyk As part of the project "Department of Works" created a server room and data transmission networks, introduced information technology digitization technologies, including new innovative solutions. In order to create more favorable conditions for the use of public services, the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the Ministry of Information Technology approved a "Cooperation Agreement".

Methods of information-analytical activity means ways to achieve more results with less effort in the implementation of information-analytical activities.

Now, if we think about the exact analysis of the crimes committed, the crime of fraud was committed in Tashkent (1921/8301), Tashkent (905/1748), Samarkand (789/1271), Syrdarya (163/526), Jizzakh (197/404), Bukhara. (779/1193), Navoi (281/483), Fergana (2274/5320), Andijan (615/1077), Namangan (655/1167), Surkhandarya (463/1010), Kashkadarya (525/905) and Karakalpakstan (331/525) in the republic due to the increase of 133.9% (10496/24554).

The highest number of frauds was registered in Fergana city - 1454, Yunusabad - 1172, Chilanzar - 1122, Mirabad 1081, 763 in Shayhantahur, 725 in Kokand, 675 in Almazar, 661 in M. Ulugbek, 631 in Yashnabad and 605 in Yakkasaray.

Theft was committed in Tashkent (966/6538), Tashkent (837/1764), Samarkand (429/749), Syrdarya (267/442), Jizzakh (178/220), Bukhara (453/843), Navoi (228/323), Fergana (2251/5041), Andijan (477/687), Namangan (613/999), Surkhandarya (386/657), Kashkadarya (419/586), Khorezm (374/425) regions and Karakalpakstan (260/411).) in the republic increased by 141.7% (8164/19732).

The highest number of thefts was in Fergana city - 1658, Chilanzar - 1096, Kokand - 1033, Yunusabad - 990, M. Ulugbek - 634, Yashnabad 519, Shayhantahur 511, Yangihayot 510, Uchtepa 469, Bektemir district 419.

Systematic work continues to strengthen the accountability and transparency of government agencies in ensuring human rights, as well as the role of civil society institutions, the media, and the political activism of the population and public associations.

However, due to the fact that the information systems of some ministries and agencies are not integrated, the inquiry and preliminary investigation bodies are required to review reports of crimes and exchange information in paper form in criminal proceedings.

This, in turn, indicates the inability to obtain timely information that is important for the prompt and complete disclosure of a crime, and leads to procedural deadlines in the work of the pre-trial investigation bodies and impedes prompt and thorough investigation of cases that need to be proven.

As a follow-up to the reforms, in order to further digitize investigative activities and establish a single electronic document exchange system in the pre-trial process, this year

A single information system, Electronic Inquiry and Preliminary Investigation, is scheduled to be launched on May 1.

DISCUSSION

Through this information system, the participants of the inquiry and preliminary investigation process will be able to quickly consider information, reports and other information about crimes in the future pre-trial stage and exchange information between government agencies and organizations to ensure the speedy receipt of information on criminal cases. gives At the same time, decisions, assignments, instructions and other notifications of inquirers and investigators are sent to the relevant government agencies and organizations in the form of electronic documents.

Procedures for confiscation of property of suspects, accused, timely implementation of restrictive measures established by the legislation with the use of information and communication technologies in order to take measures to compensate for material damage caused by criminal acts identified during the preliminary investigation of the criminal case and increase its effectiveness is introduced.

The advantages of introducing this system are that

- A special electronic database of criminal cases in the proceedings of investigators and inquirers and the materials of the pre-investigation investigation will be created;

- A total of 29 ministries and organizations will receive online inquiries, which will be available online within 1 day;

- In the framework of a criminal case, an electronic system of registration and seizure of property and a ban on the departure of the suspect or accused from the state border will be

created, which will limit the concealment of this category of persons from the investigation and court;

- As a result of the possibility to summon the participants of the proceedings to the investigation process via online SMS notification, the time of investigators and inquirers will be saved and the paper form of the summons will be completely abandoned;

- The practice of electronic generation of more than 25 analytical reports on the results of the preliminary investigation of criminal cases in the proceedings of investigators and inquiry officers within 30 seconds will be introduced;

- The Investigation Department will be able to control crimes and request information on the investigation process from the responsible officials by the 15th of each month, the implementation of written instructions issued by higher criminal authorities and methods of its control in electronic form.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the above considerations, as a result of the information analysis, it would be appropriate to mention the following as recommendations for determining the future prospects of the activities of law enforcement agencies:

first, the information-analytical activity of the internal affairs bodies is an important tool for its transformation into a popular and modern structure;

secondly, it is based on the assessment and monitoring of the level of information and analytical activities in the maintenance of public order and the successful implementation of the fight against crime in each district (city) or region;

thirdly, to study and analyze the nature of events and processes in the administrative territory, their causes and impact on the state and nature of the criminogenic situation through the use of information and analytical activities in the country, to provide information on the operational situation and eliminate negative factors serves to activate the definition of the main directions of work in the field of education;

fourth, the creative effect of information-analytical activity in the system of internal affairs, as a result of which through the study of relevant data, individual facts become the final finished product (information) that helps to organize the relevant work, and targeted use becomes an important source for scientific predictions.

fifth, it can be seen as an important communication system in evaluating the work done by managers during their service in recent years and for further improving cooperation between law enforcement agencies.

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